

Common Fixed Point Theorem in Sequentially Complete Hausdorff Ordered Uniform Spaces

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we obtain coincidence point and common fixed point theorem for contraction type mappings satisfying a contractive inequality using generalized altering distance function in ordered uniform spaces. In this paper I considering sequentially complete Hausdorff ordered Uniform space, four sequentially continuous mappings and their pairs are compatible and two mappings are increasing with respect to other two.

Keywords: Ordered uniform space, Coincident point, Common fixed point, Compatible pair of mappings, Altering distance function, Generalized weakly C-contraction.

INTRODUCTION

The well known Banach fixed point theorem for contraction mapping has been generalized and extended in many directions. Since the uniform spaces form a natural extension of the metric spaces, there exists a considerable literature of fixed point theory dealing with results on fixed or common fixed points in uniform spaces.

A new category of fixed point problems was addressed by Khan *et al*¹². They introduced the notion of an altering distance function which is a control function that alters distance between two points in a metric space.

Definition 1.1¹²

The function $\psi: [0, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ is called an altering distance function, if the following properties are satisfied:

- (i) ψ is continuous and non decreasing,
- (ii) $\psi(t) = 0$ if and only if $t = 0$.

Altering distance has been used in metric fixed point theory in recent papers^{3,6,11,14}. Choudhury² also introduced the following definition.

Definition 1.2²

A $f: X \rightarrow X$ mapping, where (X, d) is a metric space is said to be weakly C-contraction if for all $x, y \in X$, the following inequality holds:

$$d(fx, fy) \leq \frac{1}{2} [d(x, fy) + d(y, fx)] - \varphi(d(x, fy), d(y, fx))$$

Where $\varphi: [0, +\infty)^2 \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ is a continuous function such that $\varphi(s, t) = 0$ if and only if $s = t = 0$.

In² the author proves that if X is complete then every weak C-contraction has a unique fixed Point. Also fixed point theorems in partially ordered spaces and sequentially complete Hausdorff ordered uniform spaces are given in^{1,4,5,7,9,13}.

In this paper we establish some coincidence and common fixed point results for four self mappings on a Hausdorff sequentially complete ordered uniform spaces satisfying a generalized weak C-contractive condition which involves altering distance function.

Now, we recall some relevant definitions and properties.

We call a (X, U) pair to be a uniform space which consists of a non empty set X together with a uniformity U . It is well known (see Dugundji⁸ and Kelley¹⁰) that any uniform structure U on X is induced by a family D of pseudometrics on X and conversely any family D of pseudometrics on a set X induces on X a structure of uniform space U . In addition, U is Hausdorff if and only if D is separating. A family $D = \{d_\alpha: \alpha \in A\}$ of pseudometrics on X is said to be separating if for each pair of points $x, y \in X$ with $x \neq y$, there is a $\alpha \in A$ such that $d_\alpha(x, y) \neq 0$.

Consider a uniform space (X, U) with a uniformity U induced by a family $D = \{d_\alpha: \alpha \in A\}$ of pseudometrics on X . A sequence $\{x_n\}$ of elements in X is said to be Cauchy if for every $\varepsilon > 0$ and $\alpha \in A$, there is an N with $d_\alpha(x_n, x_{n+k}) < \varepsilon$ for all $n \geq N$ and $k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. The sequence $\{x_n\}$ is called convergent if there exists an $x_0 \in X$ such for every $\varepsilon > 0$ and $\alpha \in A$, there is an N with $d_\alpha(x_n, x_0) < \varepsilon$ for all $n \geq N$. A uniform space

is called sequentially complete if any Cauchy sequence is convergent. A subset of X is said to be sequentially closed if it contains the limit of any convergent sequence of its elements.

Let X be a non-empty set, $f, g, h, s: X \rightarrow X$ are given self mappings on X . If $w = fx = gx = hx = sx$ for some $x \in X$, then x is called a coincidence point of f, g, h and s , and w is called a point of coincidence of f, g, h and s . If $w = x$, then x is called a common fixed point of f, g, h and s .

Definition 1.3⁷

Let $(X, <)$ be a partially ordered set. Two mappings are said to be weakly increasing if $fx < gfx$ and $gx < fgx$ for all $x \in X$.

Let X be a non-empty set and $h, s: X \rightarrow X$ be a given mapping. For every $x \in X$, we denote by $h^{-1}(x)$ and $s^{-1}(x)$ the subset of X defined by:

$$h^{-1}(x) = \{u \in X | h(u) = x\}$$

$$\text{And } s^{-1}(x) = \{u \in X | s(u) = x\}$$

Definition 1.4

Let $f, g, h, s: X \rightarrow X$ are given self mappings on X . The pair (f, g) is said to be compatible if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_\alpha(fgx_n, gfx_n) = 0$ for each $\alpha \in A$, whenever $\{x_n\}$ is a sequence in X such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} fx_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} gx_n = t$ for some $t \in X$.

MAIN RESULT

Theorem 2.1

Let $(X, U, <)$ be a sequentially complete Hausdorff ordered uniform space. Let $f, g, h, s: X \rightarrow X$ be given mapping satisfying.

$$(i) \quad fX \subseteq hX, gX \subseteq kX,$$

- (ii) f, g, h and s are sequentially continuous,
- (iii) the pairs (f, h) and (g, k) are compatible,
- (iv) f and g are weakly increasing with respect to h and k .

Suppose that for every $\alpha \in A$ and $x, y \in X$ such that hx and ky are comparable, we have.

$$\psi_\alpha(d_\alpha(fx, gy)) \leq \psi_\alpha\left(\frac{1}{2}[d_\alpha(hx, gy) + d_\alpha(ky, fx)]\right) - \varphi_\alpha(d_\alpha(hx, gy) + d_\alpha(ky, fx))$$

Where for each $\alpha \in A, \psi_\alpha: [0, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ is an altering distance function and $\varphi_\alpha: [0, +\infty)^2 \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ is a continuous function with $\varphi_\alpha(s, t) = 0$ if and only if $t = s = 0$.

Then f, g, h and k have a coincidence point $u \in X$, that is, $fu = gu = hu = ku$.

Proof

Let x_0 be an arbitrary point in X . Since $fX \subseteq hX$, there exists $x_1 \in X$ such that $hx_1 = fx_0$. Since $gX \subseteq kX$, there exists $x_2 \in X$ such that $kx_2 = gx_1$. Continuing this process, we can construct sequences $\{x_n\}$ and $\{y_n\}$ in X defined by.

$$y_{2n} = fx_{2n} = hx_{2n+1}, \quad y_{2n+1} = gx_{2n+1} = kx_{2n+2} \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \dots 2$$

By construction, we have $x_{2n+1} \in h^{-1}(fx_{2n})$ and $x_{2n+2} \in k^{-1}(gx_{2n+1})$, then using the fact that f and g are weakly increasing with respect to h and k , we obtain.

$$\begin{aligned} hx_{2n+1} = fx_{2n} < gx_{2n+1} = kx_{2n+2} \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \cup \{0\} \\ kx_{2n+2} = gx_{2n+1} < fx_{2n+2} = hx_{2n+3} \quad \text{Then} \\ hx_1 < hx_2 < \dots < hx_n < hx_{n+1} < \dots \quad \text{Or} \\ y_0 < y_1 < \dots < y_{n-1} < y_n < \dots \end{aligned}$$

Since hx_{2n} and hx_{2n+1} are comparable for each $\alpha \in A$ by inequality (1), we have.

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_\alpha(d_\alpha(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1})) &= \psi_\alpha(d_\alpha(fx_{2n}, gx_{2n+1})) \\ &\leq \psi_\alpha\left(\frac{1}{2}[d_\alpha(hx_{2n}, gx_{2n+1}) + d_\alpha(fx_{2n}, kx_{2n+1})]\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \psi_\alpha(d_\alpha(hx_{2n}, gx_{2n+1}), d_\alpha(fx_{2n}, kx_{2n+1})) \\ &= \psi_\alpha\left(\frac{1}{2}[d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1}) + d_\alpha(y_{2n}, y_{2n})]\right) \dots 3 \\ &= \psi_\alpha(d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1}), d_\alpha(y_{2n}, y_{2n})) \\ &= \psi_\alpha\left(\frac{1}{2}d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1})\right) - \varphi_\alpha(d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1}), 0) \\ &\leq \psi_\alpha\left(\frac{1}{2}d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1})\right) \end{aligned}$$

Since ψ_α is a non decreasing function, we get that.

$$d_\alpha(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}) \leq \frac{1}{2}d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1})$$

By triangular inequality, we have.

$$d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1}) \leq d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}) + d_\alpha(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1})$$

$$\dots 4 \text{ Thus}$$

$$d_\alpha(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}) \leq d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}) \dots 5$$

$$d_\alpha(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+2}) \leq d_\alpha(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}) \dots 6$$

$$d_\alpha(y_{n+1}, y_{n+2}) \leq d_\alpha(y_n, y_{n+1}) \dots 7$$

It follows that the sequence $\{d_\alpha(y_n, y_{n+1})\}$ is monotonic decreasing.

Hence, there exists $r \geq 0$ such that.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_\alpha(y_n, y_{n+1}) = r \dots 8$$

By (4) we have

$$d_\alpha(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}) \leq \frac{1}{2}d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1}) \leq \frac{1}{2}(d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}) + d_\alpha(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}))$$

$$\dots 9$$

Taking $n \rightarrow \infty$ and using (8), we get-

$$r \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2}d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1}) \leq \frac{1}{2}(r + r) \dots 10$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2}d_\alpha(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n+1}) = 2r \dots 11$$

Taking $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (3) and using the continuity of $\psi_\alpha, \varphi_\alpha$ and (8), (11) we get that-

$$\psi_\alpha(r) \leq \psi_\alpha\left(\frac{1}{2}(2r)\right) - \varphi_\alpha(2r, 0) \leq \psi_\alpha(r)$$

Which implies that $\varphi_\alpha(2r, 0) = 0$ and hence $r = 0$, so we have.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_\alpha(y_n, y_{n+1}) = 0 \quad \forall \alpha \in A \dots 12$$

To prove that $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X , it is sufficient to show that $\{y_{2n}\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. Suppose to the

contrary, that $\{y_n\}$ is not a Cauchy sequence. Then there exists $\alpha_0 \in A$ and $\varepsilon > 0$ for which we can find two subsequences $\{y_{2m(k)}\}$ and $\{y_{2n(k)}\}$ of $\{y_n\}$ such that $n(k)$ is the smallest index for which,

$$n(k) > m(k) > k, \quad d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2n(k)}) \geq \varepsilon \quad \dots\dots\dots 13$$

This means that,

$$d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2n(k)-2}) < \varepsilon \quad \dots\dots\dots 14$$

Therefore, we use (13), (14) and triangular inequality to get,

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon &\leq d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2n(k)}) \\ &\leq d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2n(k)-2}) + d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)-2}, y_{2n(k)-1}) + d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)-1}, y_{2n(k)}) \\ &\leq \varepsilon + d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)-2}, y_{2n(k)-1}) + d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)-1}, y_{2n(k)}) \end{aligned}$$

Taking $k \rightarrow \infty$ in the above inequality and using (12), we find,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2n(k)}) = \varepsilon \quad \dots\dots\dots 15$$

On the other hand, we have,

$$|d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)-1}, y_{2n(k)}) - d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2n(k)})| \leq d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)-1}, y_{2n(k)})$$

Taking $k \rightarrow \infty$ in the above inequality and using (12), (15) we find,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)-1}, y_{2n(k)}) = \varepsilon \quad \dots\dots\dots 16$$

On the other hand, we have,

$$d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2n(k)}) \leq d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2n(k)+1}) + d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)+1}, y_{2n(k)})$$

Taking $k \rightarrow \infty$ in the above inequality and using (12), (15) we have,

$$\varepsilon \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2n(k)+1}) \quad \dots\dots\dots 17$$

Also, by triangular inequality, we have,

$$d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2n(k)}) \leq d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2m(k)-1}) + d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)-1}, y_{2n(k)+1}) + d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)+1}, y_{2n(k)})$$

Taking again $k \rightarrow \infty$ in the above inequality and using (12), (15) and (16) we find,

$$\varepsilon \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)-1}, y_{2n(k)+1})$$

Similarly, we can show that,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)-1}, y_{2n(k)+1}) \leq \varepsilon$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2m(k)-1}, y_{2n(k)+1}) = \varepsilon \quad \dots\dots\dots 18$$

From (1), we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{\alpha_0}(d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)+1}, y_{2m(k)})) &= \psi_{\alpha_0}(d_{\alpha_0}(f^{X_{2n(k)}}, g^{X_{2m(k)-1}})) \\ &\leq \psi_{\alpha_0}\left(\frac{1}{2}[d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)}, g^{X_{2m(k)-1}}) + d_{\alpha_0}(f^{X_{2n(k)}}, y_{2m(k)-1})]\right) \\ &\quad - \varphi_{\alpha_0}(d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)}, g^{X_{2m(k)-1}}), d_{\alpha_0}(f^{X_{2n(k)}}, y_{2m(k)-1})) \\ &\quad \dots\dots\dots 19 \\ &= \psi_{\alpha_0}\left(\frac{1}{2}[d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k)}) + d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)+1}, y_{2m(k)-1})]\right) \\ &\quad - \varphi_{\alpha_0}(d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k)}), d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)+1}, y_{2m(k)-1})) \\ &\leq \psi_{\alpha_0}\left(\frac{1}{2}[d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k)}) + d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)+1}, y_{2m(k)-1})]\right) \end{aligned}$$

Since ψ_{α_0} is a non decreasing function, we get that,

$$\psi_{\alpha_0}(d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)+1}, y_{2m(k)})) \leq \frac{1}{2}[d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k)}) + d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)+1}, y_{2m(k)-1})]$$

Taking again $k \rightarrow \infty$ in the above inequality and using (15), (18) we find,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)+1}, y_{2m(k)}) \leq \varepsilon \quad \dots\dots\dots 20$$

Therefore, from (17) and (20) we have,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_{\alpha_0}(y_{2n(k)+1}, y_{2m(k)}) = \varepsilon \quad \dots\dots\dots 21$$

Taking $k \rightarrow \infty$ in (19) and using (15), (18), (21) and the continuity of we find ψ_{α_0} and φ_{α_0} , we get that,

$$\psi_{\alpha_0}(\varepsilon) \leq \psi_{\alpha_0}\left(\frac{1}{2}(\varepsilon + \varepsilon)\right) - \varphi_{\alpha_0}(\varepsilon, \varepsilon) \leq \psi_{\alpha_0}\left(\frac{1}{2}(\varepsilon + \varepsilon)\right)$$

Which implies that $\varphi_{\alpha_0}(\varepsilon, \varepsilon) = 0$, a contradiction. Thus $\{y_{2n}\}$ is a Cauchy sequence and hence $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence.

Since (X, U) sequentially complete Hausdorff uniform space, there is $u \in X$ such that,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n = u$$

Therefore,

$$d_{\alpha}(y_n, u) \rightarrow 0 \quad \forall \alpha \in A \quad \dots\dots\dots 22$$

From the sequentially continuity of h and k , we get,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} h(y_n) = hu$$

Therefore,

$$d_{\alpha}(h(y_n), hu) \rightarrow 0. \quad \forall \alpha \in A \quad \dots\dots\dots 23$$

The triangular inequality and (2) yields,

$$\begin{aligned}
 d_\alpha(hu, fu) &\leq d_\alpha(hu, h(hx_{2n+1})) + d_\alpha(h(hx_{2n}), f(hx_{2n})) + d_\alpha(f(hx_{2n}), fu) \\
 d_\alpha(ku, gu) &\leq d_\alpha(ku, h(kx_{2n+2})) + d_\alpha(h(kx_{2n+1}), g(kx_{2n+1})) + d_\alpha(g(kx_{2n+1}), gu) \\
 \forall \alpha \in A &\dots\dots\dots 24
 \end{aligned}$$

From (2) and (22),

$$\begin{aligned}
 d_\alpha(hx_{2n}, u) \rightarrow 0, \quad d_\alpha(fx_{2n}, u) \rightarrow 0, \quad \forall \alpha \in A \\
 d_\alpha(kx_{2n+1}, u) \rightarrow 0, \quad d_\alpha(gx_{2n+1}, u) \rightarrow 0, \quad \dots\dots\dots 25
 \end{aligned}$$

The pair (f, h) and (g, k) is compatible, then,

$$d_\alpha(h(fx_{2n}), f(hx_{2n})) \rightarrow 0, \quad d_\alpha(k(gx_{2n+1}), g(kx_{2n+1})) \rightarrow 0. \quad \forall \alpha \in A$$

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Using the sequentially continuity of f, g and (25), we have,

$$d_\alpha(f(hx_{2n}), fu) \rightarrow 0, \quad d_\alpha(g(kx_{2n+1}), gu) \rightarrow 0, \quad \forall \alpha \in A$$

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Combining (23), (26) together with (27) and taking $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (24), we obtain,

$$d_\alpha(hu, fu) \leq 0, \quad d_\alpha(ku, gu) \leq 0 \quad \forall \alpha \in A$$

Which means that $hu = fu$ and $gu = ku$. So u is a coincidence point of f, g, h and k .

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